

Convergence in Diet Pattern, Food Diversity and Calorie Intake: An Analysis of Two Southern States of India

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Dr.R.Santhosh

*Assistant Professor at the Department of Economics
University College, Thiruvananthapuram, Kerala.*

Introduction

Food is a prime item of family budget across all income strata, especially for the poor. It is a fact that there exists spatial and interpersonal disparity in the expenditure on food, intake of food and calorie across the world (Morrison, Trisalyn & Aleck, 2011). There are many factors to influence and shape the diet pattern of a society. Of the many factors, change in income, urbanization and resultant lifestyle changes are being key factors. Diet pattern across the world shows that as income increases people tend to maximize their intake of nutrients by spending more on easily available staples. As people get richer they buy more food and also diversify their diet. When they get a chance to spend more on food, they do not put everything into one type of food for getting more calories from the same staples. On the other hand, they buy better tasting, more expensive calories (Banerjee & Duflo, 2011). It results in the diversification of diet. To have diverse types of food is an internationally recommended protocol for a healthy diet. Empirical evidence shows that diverse diets are accompanied by positive health outcomes (Rashid, Lisa & Tauhidur, 2006). Studies on food diversity (FD) also reveal that diet quality improves with FD since no single food can contain all the nutrients. As the number of food groups consumed increases the nutritional quality of the food increases. It is a fact that diet diversification is essential since cereals and other starchy food provides us more energy, while meat, fish and pulses enrich our food with proteins which is essential for both physical and cognitive health. Fruits and vegetables provide essential vitamins for our bodily functions. Thus, a diet diversification makes our diet a balanced one and a balanced diet is essential for our overall wellbeing. That is why Kennedy et al; (2009) argued that, a diet which is sufficiently diverse may reflect nutrient adequacy. Thus dietary diversity can be viewed as a proxy for food security.

In the post liberalized regime, the Monthly Per capita Consumption Expenditure (MPCE) on food and non-food items have registered an impressive growth in absolute as well as in real terms across different income strata of almost all States of the Union of India (Baiju 2002, Santhosh ,2013). In the literature on diet pattern, a fall in the proportion

of expenditure on cereals and a simultaneous increase in the expenditure on other food items are indexed as an improvement in the diet quality. A perusal of Consumer Expenditure Survey data of National Sample Survey Organisation (NSS) for the period 1993–94 to 2011–12 exhibits a noticeable divide in the expenditure on food, diet pattern, its diversity and calorific intake profile of various states of India. Yet, in the post liberalised regime, Southern States have achieved a remarkable improvement in their diet quality and food diversity (Santhosh, 2018). Kerala and Tamil Nadu (TN) are two leading southern states of the union of India in spearheading for such a rally. However, wide spread inequality exists in the expenditure on food across different income groups. Against this backdrop, this paper attempts to examine whether there is any improvement in the quality of diet, FD, calorie intake and any signal of convergence among different urban income strata of Kerala and TN during the period 1993–94 to 2011–12.

Data Source and Methodology

The study is based on secondary data only. The vital data source is the Consumer Expenditure Survey (CES) reports provided by the NSSO for two quinquennial rounds (NSS 50th (1993–94), and 68th (2011–12)). For an in-depth analysis and to portray the contrast and similarities in the level and pattern of food consumption among different income strata the technique of fractile group analysis is used (As reported in NSS data). F1 is called bottom fractile (lowest 5 percent of the population) and F12 (the top 5 percent population) is termed as top fractile. The bottom 4 fractile are collectively termed as Bottom Groups or the lowest 30 per cent of the population, next four fractile are termed as Middle Group or the middle 40 per cent of the population. The top 4 fractile are termed as Top Group or the top 30 per cent of the population. For the sake of simplicity, these groups are loosely called as the poor, middle and the rich respectively.

Food diversity is the average number of food items consumed by a household out of the total number of food items in a reference period of one month. In the study, food variety (FD) is estimated by using Simpson Diversity Index (SDI). Simpson Diversity Index (SDI) = $1 - \sum w_i^2$, where $\sum w_i^2$ is the sum of squares of the expenditure share or calorie share of food group 'i'. The SDI value ranges from zero to one. Higher the value of SDI, higher will be the FD and vice versa (Nguyen and Winters, 2011). Expenditure on food items in the study has been sub-divided into 14 broad groups starting from cereals to beverages and processed foods. For the comparative study Per Consumer Unit Intake of Calorie (PCUI) is taken into consideration. Period of study is from 1993–94 to 2011–12.

Results and Discussion

This section is divided into three parts. The first sub-section analyses the inter-class and intra-class inequality in the expenditure on food among different rural and urban income strata and the dietary shift during the study period. In the next section an attempt is made to discuss the disparity in FD and changes on it. In the last section inter- and intra-class inequality in calorie intake is analyzed.

Dietary Shift and Inter- and Intra- Class Disparity in the Expenditure on Food

This sub-section discusses the dietary shift that has taken place among different urban MPCE classes during the period in the form of changes in the percentage allocation of expenditure on food for both the States. A perusal of NSS data for the period from 1993–94 to 2011–12 reveals that there occurred considerable changes in the diet pattern of different urban income strata of Kerala and TN since there is a change in the allocation of expenditure on different food items (Table 1 & 2). It is also evident that there exists inter and intra-class disparity in the percentage allocation of expenditure on different food items across different income strata (Table 1). A drastic reduction in the proportion of expenditure on cereals across different income strata of Kerala and TN is observed during the period. Such a fall is more pronounced among the poor since the top income groups are already in the saturation level in the intake of cereals. Even a 16 percent reduction is recorded in the expenditure on cereals among the poor. In the literature on dietary pattern, a

near 50 or more percent of the total expenditure or more on cereals is being considered as poor quality of dietary pattern. In the year 1993–4 more than 40 per cent of the expenditure of the poor-income strata of TN was on cereals whereas in 2011–12 it falls to roughly 23 to 27 percent. It exhibits an improvement in the dietary pattern and a radical shift in the diet pattern of TN. the same is exactly true about Kerala. There exists considerable inter-class and intra-class inequality in the allocation of expenditure on cereals, albeit convergence on it is visible during the period. In Kerala, during the period 2011-12, the largest items of expenditure for the middle and top income group is not cereals but beverages and processed food. In TN, during the same period, both poor and middle income group expended a largest share of their expenditure on cereals where as the top income group on beverages and processed food. It shows the extent of diversification and change in diet pattern as well as an improvement in urban die pattern of Kerala compared to

Table 1: Percentage allocation of expenditure (0.00%) on each broad group of food items 1993-94 to 2011-12 Kerala (Urban)

Food items	F1	F2	F3	F4	F5	F6	F7	F8	F9	F10	F11	F12	ALL
Cereals	21.19 (37.32)	19.33 (37.55)	19.23 (33.99)	17.82 (32.54)	15.71 (29.97)	15.72 (28.19)	16.11 (27.78)	15.45 (25.27)	14.42 (23.21)	12.78 (19.57)	12.38 (16.27)	12.30 (13.81)	15.06 (24.09)
Gram	1.19 (0.53)	0.95 (0.59)	1.09 (0.59)	1.02 (0.53)	0.84 (0.51)	0.82 (0.54)	0.90 (0.57)	0.85 (0.56)	0.67 (0.49)	0.57 (0.68)	0.62 (0.62)	0.64 (0.58)	0.78 (0.58)
Cereal substitutes	0.47 (1.71)	0.37 (1.42)	0.38 (1.58)	0.41 (1.24)	0.47 (0.70)	0.61 (1.02)	0.54 (0.78)	0.43 (0.73)	0.52 (0.55)	0.40 (0.45)	0.48 (0.47)	0.21 (0.27)	0.44 (0.70)
Pulses	4.74 (1.57)	4.70 (2.24)	4.51 (2.33)	4.50 (2.87)	4.21 (2.75)	4.05 (3.11)	3.87 (3.04)	4.14 (3.24)	3.27 (3.32)	3.58 (3.19)	3.30 (3.00)	3.10 (2.99)	3.82 (3.03)
Milk & products	7.48 (4.44)	9.50 (4.24)	9.12 (6.78)	10.10 (7.32)	10.47 (6.34)	11.71 (8.75)	11.00 (9.41)	12.09 (10.59)	13.10 (11.16)	12.24 (11.89)	12.46 (13.93)	13.02 (14.11)	11.60 (10.39)
Sugar	3.54 (5.59)	3.45 (4.83)	3.56 (4.83)	3.26 (4.71)	3.32 (4.59)	2.84 (4.32)	2.77 (4.26)	2.55 (4.03)	2.17 (3.93)	1.84 (3.88)	2.13 (3.68)	1.68 (3.13)	2.53 (4.06)
Salt	0.37 (0.34)	0.34 (0.28)	0.31 (0.27)	0.30 (0.25)	0.28 (0.23)	0.28 (0.21)	0.25 (0.19)	0.23 (0.18)	0.19 (0.22)	0.17 (0.16)	0.15 (0.15)	0.15 (0.14)	0.23 (0.20)
Edible oil	6.13 (5.21)	6.69 (5.24)	6.36 (5.59)	5.69 (5.19)	5.61 (5.30)	5.36 (4.86)	5.32 (4.79)	4.94 (4.82)	4.02 (4.96)	3.80 (4.75)	3.35 (4.21)	2.99 (4.08)	4.65 (4.78)
Egg fish & meat	19.93 (12.20)	17.86 (13.02)	17.57 (15.13)	18.99 (13.18)	19.25 (13.45)	19.19 (13.44)	20.22 (14.75)	19.27 (15.99)	17.11 (15.32)	17.50 (16.12)	17.68 (16.25)	19.58 (14.95)	18.58 (15.04)
Vegetable	7.08 (5.20)	6.67 (7.11)	7.28 (5.48)	6.66 (6.50)	7.10 (5.94)	6.77 (6.27)	6.36 (6.27)	6.71 (6.67)	5.58 (6.38)	6.03 (6.37)	6.18 (6.80)	6.05 (6.37)	6.40 (6.35)
Fruits(fresh)	8.09 (9.28)	9.07 (7.88)	8.55 (8.47)	9.14 (9.38)	10.09 (9.22)	9.06 (9.33)	8.82 (9.98)	9.94 (10.18)	9.03 (10.03)	10.36 (10.23)	9.96 (11.36)	10.66 (10.11)	9.60 (9.93)
Fruits (dry)	0.04 (0.00)	0.16 (0.00)	0.34 (0.05)	0.28 (0.04)	0.50 (0.07)	0.51 (0.18)	0.70 (0.24)	0.54 (0.30)	0.64 (0.13)	1.20 (0.35)	1.13 (0.59)	1.95 (0.72)	0.81 (0.29)
Spices	5.57 (5.15)	5.81 (4.69)	6.01 (4.42)	5.49 (4.75)	5.75 (4.32)	5.51 (4.36)	5.25 (4.28)	4.68 (3.86)	4.24 (3.64)	4.11 (3.33)	3.82 (2.89)	3.38 (2.55)	4.73 (3.94)
Beverages & processed food	14.18 (11.47)	15.11 (10.90)	15.69 (10.79)	16.35 (11.48)	16.40 (16.60)	17.57 (14.94)	17.89 (13.66)	18.18 (13.48)	25.05 (15.65)	25.41 (19.02)	26.36 (19.78)	24.28 (26.18)	20.77 (16.81)
All	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00

Source: Estimated from NSS CES for 50 th and 68 th round reports. Figures in the parentheses are 1993–4 figures.

TN. Interestingly among the upper income group of Kerala, the second item of expenditure is on the broad group of egg, fish and meat, pulling the cereals in to third. In TN, the expenditure on milk is increasing but vegetable is falling during the entire period of analysis. It is also fascinating to note that as income increases expenditure on processed food and beverages is ascending at an increasing pace. Both in Kerala and TN, expenditure on milk is escalating across all groups though it is more intense among the poor signifying a dietary shift and also an improvement in diet quality. Likewise expenditure on egg, fish, and meat is also increasing at a rapid rate in Kerala but at a slower pace in TN (Table 1&2). It is obvious that a significant

reduction in the expenditure on cereals and an up in the expenditure on pulses, milk, egg, fish, and meat on a compensatory basis signifying an improvement in the diet quality of Kerala and TN during the period 1993-4 to 2011-2. It is to be noted that there is an inter-class and intra-class convergence in the allocation of expenditure on food. It is interesting to note that expenditure on edible oil is falling whereas it is increasing for the broad group egg, fish, and meat, which exhibits an improvement in the quality of dietary pattern of TN. Urban TN also shows a worrying trend of fall in the expenditure on vegetables. A shift in favour of beverages and processed food signals the next-generation shift in the consumption pattern in favour of processed, packaged and ready-to-eat food among the urban people of Kerala and TN. It is to be inferred here that there is a fall in the expenditure on cereals and an increase in the expenditure on all other broad groups of food items on a compensatory basis, signifying a radical shift in the dietary pattern as well as an improvement in the quality of diet of both Kerala and TN. It is fact that there is a wide spread inter –class and intra –class inequality in the expenditure on various broad groups of food items. Albeit, there is a clear evidence of convergence in diet pattern across the urban people of Kerala and TN.

Table 2: Percentage allocation of expenditure on each broad group of food items 1993-4 to 2011-12 TN (Urban)

Item	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	all
Cereals	27.14 (43.83)	23.48 (41.18)	23.61 (38.94)	21.02 (37.98)	21.57 (36.21)	20.92 (34.20)	20.29 (31.18)	20.05 (29.82)	18.39 (26.66)	16.62 (24.93)	14.95 (20.44)	12.55 (12.55)	19.04 (29.93)
Gram& products	0.85 (0.27)	0.84 (0.22)	1.10 (0.32)	0.99 (0.33)	0.86 (0.36)	0.83 (0.44)	0.89 (0.41)	0.77 (0.54)	0.67 (0.44)	0.72 (0.58)	0.50 (0.34)	0.45 (0.35)	0.76 (0.42)
Cereal substitutes	0.00 (0.00)	0.03 (0.02)	0.00 (0.01)	0.03 (0.01)	0.01 (0.01)	0.02 (0.01)	0.03 (0.01)	0.04 (0.02)	0.03 (0.01)	0.01 (0.01)	0.03 (0.01)	0.00 (0.00)	0.02 (0.01)
Pulses	7.25 (5.66)	6.10 (6.15)	6.29 (6.48)	6.11 (6.30)	6.32 (6.56)	6.14 (6.47)	6.22 (6.49)	6.04 (6.78)	5.51 (6.67)	5.59 (6.44)	4.97 (5.10)	4.19 (5.17)	5.75 (6.28)
Milk& products	11.86 (4.66)	13.88 (5.59)	15.99 (6.39)	15.73 (7.51)	16.83 (9.48)	16.08 (10.04)	16.79 (10.45)	17.91 (12.31)	15.56 (13.50)	17.86 (14.88)	16.64 (14.96)	17.70 (14.69)	16.60 (11.45)
Sugar &products	2.19 (2.43)	1.92 (2.61)	2.10 (2.53)	1.90 (2.77)	1.73 (2.89)	1.83 (3.02)	1.78 (3.05)	1.75 (3.26)	1.70 (3.27)	1.62 (3.21)	1.45 (2.93)	1.31 (2.41)	1.72 (2.95)
Salt	0.50 (0.35)	0.44 (0.29)	0.43 (0.27)	0.37 (0.28)	0.35 (0.26)	0.33 (0.23)	0.32 (0.22)	0.30 (0.22)	0.27 (0.20)	0.25 (0.19)	0.22 (0.16)	0.17 (0.14)	0.30 (0.22)
Edible oil	5.30 (6.09)	5.46 (6.37)	5.60 (6.39)	5.29 (6.55)	5.41 (6.53)	5.49 (6.67)	5.12 (6.45)	5.15 (6.99)	4.72 (6.84)	4.50 (6.89)	4.01 (6.30)	3.48 (5.98)	4.86 (6.58)
Egg, fish& meat	8.04 (4.92)	9.67 (6.38)	9.31 (6.36)	10.70 (6.93)	10.04 (7.16)	11.66 (8.64)	10.75 (8.75)	10.72 (8.03)	10.36 (8.08)	8.99 (7.98)	9.65 (7.05)	6.47 (8.01)	9.81 (7.71)
Vegetables	9.47 (10.95)	9.22 (9.49)	9.60 (9.78)	9.32 (9.98)	8.50 (9.69)	9.33 (9.34)	8.46 (8.68)	8.30 (9.13)	7.53 (8.21)	7.32 (8.48)	6.45 (7.58)	4.88 (6.51)	7.94 (8.76)
Fruits (Fresh)	3.83 (2.29)	4.26 (2.77)	4.66 (2.84)	5.06 (2.90)	4.79 (3.08)	5.08 (3.49)	5.20 (3.56)	5.41 (3.80)	6.09 (4.15)	6.35 (4.56)	6.72 (5.77)	6.20 (5.50)	5.56 (3.93)
Fruits (dry)	0.25 (0.07)	0.20 (0.01)	0.26 (0.04)	0.34 (0.02)	0.30 (0.05)	0.30 (0.07)	0.36 (0.11)	0.46 (0.21)	0.65 (0.17)	0.85 (0.24)	0.98 (0.43)	0.89 (0.37)	0.55 (0.17)
Spices	8.39 (7.31)	7.44 (6.44)	7.01 (6.23)	6.85 (6.00)	6.39 (5.76)	6.14 (5.32)	6.08 (5.07)	5.95 (4.80)	5.14 (4.56)	4.97 (4.26)	4.02 (3.38)	3.17 (3.09)	5.59 (4.88)
Beverages etc	14.93 (11.17)	17.07 (12.47)	14.04 (13.41)	16.28 (12.43)	16.90 (11.96)	15.85 (12.07)	17.72 (15.57)	17.16 (14.10)	23.39 (17.24)	24.34 (17.35)	29.41 (25.55)	38.54 (30.25)	21.49 (16.72)
Total	100	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00

Source: Estimated from NSS CES for 50 th and 68 th round reports. Figures in the parentheses are 1993–4 figures.

Trend and Disparity in Food Diversity

FD shows the variety of different food items consumed and is an index of diet quality. Variety in food makes the diet a balanced one which is essential for our both physical and cognitive health. FD is derived from the percentage allocation of expenditure on different food items and the changes over it. FD is measured by using Simpson Diversity Index (SDI). FD is estimated on NSS data for the periods 1993–4 and 2011–2.

Estimated data shows that both in Kerala and in TN, FD have improved drastically for the lower- and middle-income strata since SDI value is increasing (Table 3). Such an uptrend is more pronounced among the bottom groups of TN compared to Kerala. However, Kerala is ahead of TN in FD. It is worth to note that TN has achieved outstanding and rapid increase in FD in the post liberalized regime. In both the States, a significant fall in the FD of the upper-income strata is observed during the study period as evident by the falling SDI value (Figure 1 & 2). A fall in the concentration of expenditure on cereals and an increase in the expenditure on other food items can be attributed as a cause for a significant uptrend in the FD of the poor- and middle-income groups. The reason that can be attributed for a lower FD for the upper income strata is that after a significant reduction in the expenditure on cereals, there is a highly skewed expenditure for beverages and processed food, egg, fish and meat among the top fractile. Even then the overall urban FD of Kerala and TN has improved and there is convergence in it across and among different urban income strata of Kerala and TN during the period.

Table 3 Food Diversity of Rural and Urban TN 1993–, 4- 2011–, 2

50th Round (1993–4)			68th Round (2011–2)	
Simpson Diversity Index (SDI)				
Fractile	Kerala (U)	TN(U)	Kerala (U)	TN(U)
(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)
F1	0.8103	0.7654	0.8676	0.8574
F2	0.8091	0.7851	0.8748	0.8641
F3	0.8273	0.7990	0.8755	0.8663
F4	0.8370	0.8064	0.8730	0.8701
F5	0.8408	0.8173	0.8758	0.8656
F6	0.8515	0.8286	0.8726	0.8694
F7	0.8545	0.8392	0.8692	0.8672
F8	0.8598	0.8469	0.8698	0.8667
F9	0.8618	0.8536	0.8537	0.8589
F10	0.8649	0.8681	0.8542	0.8557
F11	0.8661	0.8479	0.8503	0.8394
F12	0.8515	0.8346	0.8519	0.7897
ALL	0.8601	0.8426	0.8662	0.8617

Source: Estimated from NSS data for 50th and 68th round

Figure: 1. Food diversity by Simpson Index for Kerala and TN (Urban) 1993–4

Source: Prepared from NSS data for 50th round reports

Figure 2 Food diversity by Simpson Index for Kerala and TN (Urban) 2011-2

Source: Prepared from NSS data for 68th round reports

Trend in the per capita intake of calorie

Over the years there has been an absolute as well as real increase in the expenditure on food in both the States (Santhosh, 2018). Both an increase in the expenditure of food and a change in the percentage allocation of expenditure on various broad groups of food items have their impact on the intake of calorie among different income strata since calorie content vary across food products. A shift away from cereals to other food groups also has made a dent on the intake of calories, as cereals are the cheapest but richest source of energy. In the post-reform period the calorie intake of the poor-income group of both Kerala and TN has improved significantly (Table 4). The bottom fractile of TN has registered a 34 per cent increase in their intake of calorie whereas its Kerala counterpart has registered a 30 percent growth during the period. With respect to the Middle income group there is a less significant growth in the calorie intake in TN but it is significant in Kerala. It can also be seen that there is a noteworthy fall in the intake of calorie among the top fractile of both Kerala and TN but it is very drastic in TN.

Table 4: Per capita Per Consumer Unit per Diem intake of Calorie by fractile group

MPCE class as Fractile	NSS Rounds					Percentage growth (0.00 percent) in the intake of calorie
	50th Round (1993-94)		68th Round (2011-12)			
	Intake of calorie		Intake of calorie			
	In kcal		In kcal			
	Kerala(U)	TN (U)	Kerala (U)	TN (U)	Kerala	
(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)	(7)
F1	1251	1186	1808	1801	30.81	34.15
F2	1619	1660	2037	2046	20.52	18.87
F3	1734	1903	2033	2110	14.71	9.81
F4	1940	2012	2230	2279	13.00	11.72
F5	2134	2160	2321	2338	8.06	7.61
F6	2225	2308	2421	2395	8.10	3.63
F7	2375	2454	2616	2405	9.21	-2.04
F8	2574	2581	2684	2629	4.10	1.83
F9	2686	2697	2852	2725	5.82	1.03
F10	2950	2957	3129	2721	5.72	-8.67
F11	3476	3218	3511	2956	1.00	-8.86
F12	3813	3812	3606	3089	-5.74	-23.41
All	2445	2366	2577	2456	5.12	3.66

Source: NSS reports for 50th and 68th round

This is because of a shift in the consumption pattern against cereals (richest and cheapest source of energy) and in favour of other food groups. A much expected fall in the intake of calorie due to a shift away from cereals among the urban-income strata might have averted due to a significant growth in the expenditure on food. There is also a mismatch in the growth of MPCE on food and growth in calorie intake of the rich. It is due to the diversification of diet among the rich in favour of food other than cereals. The poor has registered a significant growth in the intake of calorie since they are spending a substantial portion of their expenditure on cereals. However, diversification of diet ensures a balanced diet and a fall in the excess intake of calorie during the period can be considered as a positive spill over. It is expected that the rich income group might have a sedentary way of life and an average intake of 3000 kcal and above per day may lead to the occurrence of lifestyle diseases. In the entire period of analysis, Kerala is ahead of the TN in the intake of calorie. Though there is an inter-class and intra-class inequality in the intake of calorie there is a clear evidence of convergence in the intake of calorie across and among different urban income strata of Kerala and TN.

Conclusion

Though food is a basic requirement, there exists a wide disparity in the expenditure on food, food diversity, and calorie intake among different strata of people of Kerala and TN. A perusal of NSS data for the period 1993–4 to 2011–2 reveals that both in Kerala and in TN there is a high concentration of expenditure on cereals in 1993–4 and there is a considerable fall in it during the period of 2011–2. With a fall in the expenditure on cereals and vegetable, expenditure on broad groups of food items like beverages and refreshments, egg, fish and meat, etc. is increasing. With respect to FD, poor- and middle-income groups have registered a drastic improvement whereas rich-income group has registered a fall. The poor has registered a significant improvement in FD during the period with a drastic reduction in the expenditure on cereals and a lift up in the allocation of expenditure on other food items. The reason for a fall in the FD of the rich-income group is a new trend of concentration of expenditure on beverages and processed foods. With respect to the calorie intake, the poor-income groups of both the states have registered an impressive growth during the period. However, the rich-income groups of TN have experienced a fall in calorie intake during this period. During the study period there is a clear evidence of inter-class and intra-class convergence in diet pattern, FD and calorie intake. One important reason which can be attributed for such a convergence is the various schemes enunciated by the government of Tamil Nadu in ensuring quality food at an affordable rate to the poor while Kerala is already in the top of FD, quality of diet and calorie intake. Care should be taken to ensure the required intake of calorie among the poor income strata by strengthening the public distribution system since they are involved in more physical and manual work. It is also imperative to create awareness among the poor and middle income groups about the importance of diversification and disseminate the information that the positive effects of diversification is enjoyable only by ensuring a baseline intake of calorie from cereals. In over all, the inter-class and intra-class convergence in diet pattern, FD and calorie intake achieved by TN compared to Kerala in a short span of time is amazing. It is cheerful to note that Kerala and TN are converging.

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